

The holy Kjeld of Viborg (older text)

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Entry tags: Miracle tales, Christianity, Christian, Latin Text, Catholic, Religious Group, Text, Hagiography, Medieval Christianity, Catholic text

The holy Kjeld of Viborg was a Danish clergyman from the 12th C. who was canonized and revered as a saint until the Danish reformation. Although he was venerated across medieval Denmark, primarily, there are signs from the middle ages that his cult also did spread into Norway, Sweden, and Northern Germany at least to some extent. In Norway his feast day has been found included in a late medieval calendar. In Northern Germany information on him has been found in at least one religious book. In Sweden, no less than 4 fragmentary liturgical manuscripts from the middle ages has been found with his cult included in them. Although one of these 4 manuscripts might be somewhat explained because it was found on Gotland, and this island was under Danish rule during the later middle ages, none of the other three manuscripts can necessarily be explained that easily. Thus although his saint's cult does not seem to have been venerated systematically across dioceses outside of Denmark, it does seem like his cult must have been known and perhaps even celebrated to some extent also in the areas neighbouring Denmark. At least this seems to have been the case within certain groups or regions, although probably not systematically all over. Possibly his cult spread because it gained a certain regional popularity in parts of the monastic world. Kjeld himself was a member of the holy chapter in Viborg diocese in Denmark and at his time that holy chapter was also an Augustinian convent. No less than two of the four medieval manuscripts found in Sweden has monastic origins, as one of them stems from the Bridgettines at Vadstena monastery and the other one seems to have roots within the Franciscan Order. According to sources St. Kjeld was born in Jutland probably quite early on during the reign of king Niels of Denmark (1104-34), and he died on 27. September 1150. He was of noble descent and his career as a clergyman was spent at the holy chapter in Viborg diocese in Denmark, where he became a cathedral canon. It also seems like he probably received some kind of formal education himself and later as canon he seems to have led the cathedral school in Viborg for a while. He ended his career at the chapter as elected dean. Later on Viborg always remained the essential center of his saint's cult. He was canonized presumably on 11. July in either 1188 or 1189 by archbishop Absalon of Lund in Denmark after Absalon had achieved papal consent and permission to let Kjeld's sanctity be examined and canonize him if this was deemed justified. The preserved text about St. Kjeld was probably written around 1187 or 1188 to coincide with his canonization process. The actual biography is followed by a list of miracles which seems to be more or less contemporary with the biographical text, as many of the miracles seem to have happened during the period from 1185 to 1187 when judging from the dates mentioned. Although the original, complete version of the text has now been lost, comprehensive excerpts are preserved. The anonymous author must have been a well educated clergyman who knew Kjeld personally, and he seems to have been a cathedral canon at the holy chapter in Viborg just like Kjeld himself had been earlier on. The text starts out by telling about his childhood, youth, and education, then continuing on with his clerical career in Viborg, the murder of bishop Eskil, his mentor, and the election of Kjeld as a dean. It goes on from there with his accomplishments during a city fire in Viborg, as a mediator during a civil war in Denmark, and his captivity with heathens. It also tells about how his generosity towards the poor was so great that he became exiled from the holy chapter for a while until being reinstated by the Pope in Rome. It concludes by telling about his death and the subsequent miracles which followed.

Date Range: 1188 CE - 1536 CE

Region: Viborg, Denmark

Region tags: Denmark

The town of Viborg in Denmark. The key location in the cult of the holy Kjeld.

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: M. Cl. Gertz: *Vitae Sanctorum Danorum*, København 1908-12
- Source 2: Henning Høirup & O.F. Stjernfeldt: *Sankt Kjeld: levned og undergerninger samt teksterne til Kjelds fest med en historisk redegørelse*, Viborg Domkirkes Forlag, Viborg, 1961

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://wiki.app.uib.no/medieval/index.php?title=Sanctus_Ketillus (background information on the text in English)

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: A scanned edition of Gertz's book is available online

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: On parchment originally, nowadays preserved on paper.

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Notes: The original manuscript must have been written on parchment.

↳ Specify type of paper

- Specify: The original manuscript is not preserved: it is written on paper in the preserved form, but the original manuscript must have been written on parchment

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Other [specify]: The original parchment must have been physically prepared in advance of cause

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

- Other [specify]: The original manuscript is not preserved

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Notes: The answer seems to be yes and no at the same time. As his cult spread and manuscripts have been found on different locations, the text was obviously not stored in just one specific location. However, his cult centered on Viborg cathedral where the text was also written at the holy chapter there. A manuscript thus must have been stored there and the miracle list naturally seems to have been connected to his tomb within the cathedral.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Notes: It can be imagined that there may have been mural paintings of him in the cathedral during medieval times, but they are not preserved. He has been pictured elsewhere, though, and a mural painting of him is preserved in a church in Skive within Viborg diocese.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: Perhaps the answer is yes and no at the same time. The anonymous canon who wrote it was not necessarily paid for it, but he was financially dependent on the holy chapter as a member of it, and the holy chapter undoubtedly gained financially from the cult of St. Kjeld.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: This depends on definition. The older text was undoubtedly considered to be the official saint's vita about St. Kjeld and its content was reused e.g. as basis for the writing of texts for the later liturgical celebrations of him. However, Kjeld's cult was only a regional phenomenon thus neither the text nor him was known throughout medieval Europe.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: written in latin

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Notes: Depends on definition. The holy chapter, of course, gained new members from time to time.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Notes: The text formed the basis of the texts for the later liturgical celebrations of St. Kjeld.

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– No

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– No

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– No

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: liturgical celebrations

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Field doesn't know

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: Not known exactly, but it seems that he must have been celebrated at least once yearly on 11. July (the date of his canonization).

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

- ↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?
 - No

Is there material significance to the text?

- No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

- Field doesn't know

Notes: The original manuscript is not preserved.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

- Yes

- ↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?
 - Yes

- ↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?
 - Yes

Notes: There was not necessarily more than one version of the older text, but different liturgical texts (based on the older text) and also a younger text about him came into existence. It seems like the older text continued to have authority as the official one (as it was used as basis for the liturgical celebrations), but this does not necessarily mean that e.g. the younger text then was disregarded as improper.

- ↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?
 - No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

- Yes

- ↳ Is there a sense of canonization?
 - Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: The text is attached to an official canonization and thus establishes itself as the official text about him.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: Yes in the sense that e.g. a younger text on St. Kjeld also was written. No in the sense that the older text probably continued to be considered the official one.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– No

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Notes: Although yes in the sense that also hagiography contains this element.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: hagiography

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: none of the above

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: Although yes in the sense that it mentions that Kjeld died on 27. september thereby setting the stage for him being celebrated as a saint on that day.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: But his death is described

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Notes: But there are stories of miracles happening at his grave

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: none of the above

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)
– No

↳ Courage (generic)
– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Notes: cf notes below regarding welfare

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– No

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)
– No

↳ Power/status/nobility
– Yes
Notes: He is of noble birth

↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– No

↳ Optimism/hope
– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Although obviously Kjeld's life as a cleric did

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Notes: Although Kjeld's life as a cleric must have done so.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: But it contains a story where Kjeld through prayer miraculously prevents the buildings of the institution from burning during a city fire.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: The text was written by an anonymous canon at the holy chapter in Viborg diocese

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Obviously the text must have spread from Viborg diocese.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: none of the above

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Notes: Poverty relief has an important place in this text, but not in the institutionalized form. The text tells widely about how Kjeld himself was very generous towards the poor in order to help them. When he received gold and a valuable ring from the king, he gave it away to the poor. He also often gave away his own clothes in order to help out the poor. According to the text his generosity was so great that he ended up being at odds with the religious institution that he belonged to and he actually ended up being ousted and exiled from it for a while until by remorse they reconciled and took him back on papal orders.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Notes: Not in the institutionalized form, but it tells about how Kjeld personally gave away his own cloak to a crippled naked leper.

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Notes: But Kjeld was considered an officially canonized saint across Denmark and the text thus was probably taught at least within Viborg diocese

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: However, Kjeld's clerical education is described and this is done in such ways that this indicate that the anonymous writer is likely to have either received university education himself or that he at least must have had close knowledge of how the university education of that day and age was organized and what was taught there (cf. e.g. his descriptions of the liberal arts education and also the fact that the author refers to the works of Aristotle which he have clearly read himself). The text also indicates that Kjeld himself at some point probably taught at the cathedral school in Viborg by mentioning his apprentices.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– Yes

Notes: It describes Kjeld's position at the cathedral school and mentions his apprentices. The author also cites one specified apprentice as a source of information on Kjeld.

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Notes: The text mentions warfare because there was a civil war between two rival kings going on in Denmark at Kjeld's time. It describes how homicide and persecution increased everywhere and how his prayers led to the re-establishing of peace when he visited one of the

kings.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

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